

ARCSS Program | Message from the ARCSS Committee

ARCSS Note #12 (7 August 2008): eTown Meeting Announcement: Changing Seasonality

- **ARCSS Community eTown Meeting**
- "Changing Seasonality in the Arctic System"
- **Date:** Tuesday, 19 August 2008
- **Time:** 11:00 a.m. Alaska Daylight Time (AKDT)
- (12:00 p.m. PDT; 1:00 p.m. MDT; 2:00 p.m. CDT; 3:00 p.m. EDT)
- **Duration:** Approximately 1.5 hours

Advance registration is required.

- **Registration Deadline:** Thursday, 14 August 2008

eTown Meeting overview and registration available at: http://www.arcus.org/arcss/etm/august_08/index.html
(http://www.arcus.org/arcss/etm/august_08/index.html)

For further information, please contact:

- **Helen Wiggins, ARCUS**
- Phone: 907-474-1600
- Email: helen@arcus.org

The ARCSS Committee announces a community eTown Meeting focused on "Changing Seasonality in the Arctic System." Through an ARCSS Community of Practice and discussions at several community venues, including the ARCSS Synthesis Workshop in October 2007, the topic of changing seasonality has emerged as a priority for understanding the arctic system, and the NSF ARCSS Program has recently announced a "Changing Seasonality in the Arctic System (CSAS)" research solicitation (http://www.nsf.gov/funding/pgm_summ.jsp?pims_id=503195 (http://www.nsf.gov/funding/pgm_summ.jsp?pims_id=503195)).

The timing and dynamics of key events such as spring melt and fall freeze-up are shifting in response to a changing arctic climate, impacting the interconnected physical, biological, and human components and processes of the arctic system. Thus, to gain predictability and understanding of the Arctic, more knowledge is needed of changes in the seasonal timing and synchrony of events that are critical to the functioning of the system.

This eTown Meeting will provide an open community forum to discuss the development of the "Changing Seasonality" effort, a community vision for interdisciplinary seasonality science, and ARCSS-relevant seasonality science questions that address system-level understanding.

This eTown Meeting is scheduled for Tuesday, 19 August 2008, at 11:00 a.m. Alaska Daylight Time (AKDT) (12:00 p.m. PDT; 1:00 p.m. MDT; 2:00 p.m. CDT; 3:00 p.m. EDT).

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

To join the eTown Meeting, participants will login to an Internet presentation AND call in through a teleconference line, though participants also have the option to participate via phone only. Internet-platform login and teleconference call-in instructions will be sent to all registered participants in advance. The eTown Meeting will be archived and available for viewing after the actual online session.

Registration Deadline: Thursday, 14 August 2008 eTown Meeting overview and registration available at:
http://www.arcus.org/arcss/etm/august_08/index.html (http://www.arcus.org/arcss/etm/august_08/index.html)